

Introduction: Commercial lunar missions require rigorous, multi-criteria landing site selection spanning a wide range of spatial scales, from global candidate screening down to metre-level hazard assessment. No single tool covers this full analytical chain, and in practice the workflow combines automated geospatial analysis with expert manual interpretation in GIS software.

At ispace Europe, we have developed a Mission Planning Toolkit to support this workflow, alongside a broader set of standalone tools and geospatial processes applied across mission phases.

Methodology: The analytical methodology follows a three-stage approach. At the global and regional scale, spatial constraints such as latitude requirements, slope, terrain roughness, and crater density are evaluated by combining planetary datasets within GIS software (ArcGIS Pro, QGIS) and custom Python scripts. At the local scale, detailed analysis of candidate sites involves high-resolution slope and roughness mapping, hazard identification, approach corridor assessment, and shadow analysis at approximately 1 m/pixel resolution.

Throughout all stages, Sun and Earth visibility calculations are performed using NAIF/SPICE at daily time steps for general analysis and hourly resolution for detailed assessments, producing horizon mask plots, annual visibility profiles, and temporal illumination maps, which are critical inputs for assessing energy availability and communications coverage at any given site and mission window.

Results: The Mission Planning Toolkit consolidates several of these capabilities into an integrated interface. Individual tools address specific planning needs: a horizon mask tool computing terrain-occulted Sun and Earth trajectories at a given surface point, a mission window calculator identifying optimal landing dates from visibility constraints, a ground station coverage tool, and a map-based search interface for retrieving and georeferencing high-resolution NAC imagery.

The toolkit is under active development, with an updated unified web interface and a distributed geospatial database in progress to centralise datasets and outputs across tools and offices. Manual GIS analysis remains central to the detailed stages of the workflow, where expert interpretation and site validation complement the outputs of automated tools.

Conclusion: This toolchain was applied in full to the Hakuto-R lunar missions Mission 1 (M1) and Mission 2 (M2) landing site selection and planning processes, covering the complete analytical chain from initial site screening to final candidate validation.

Preparation work for Mission 4 is currently ongoing, with 3 candidate sites under evaluation and continued improvements to the toolkit and analysis workflow.

Together, these missions represent the practical application of an integrated, scalable approach to commercial lunar mission planning, and the toolchain presented here is designed to be adaptable to a broad range of future lunar landing objectives.